

NanOx4EStor

Nanoscaled ferroelectric (pseudo)-binary oxide thin film supercapacitors for flexible and ultrafast pulsed power electronics

At a Glance

Funded under: M-ERA.NET3

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Coordinated by: University of Minho, Portugal

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The Project

The main goal of the **NanOx4EStor** project is to develop innovative and cost effective high-throughput technologies for the fabrication of advanced supercapacitors based on wake-up free (pseudo)-binary oxide thin films, fabricated by physical vapour deposition (PVD) processes, with optimized ferroelectric and energy storage (ES) properties through (i) strain, (ii) interface and (iii) dead-layer engineering.

Consortium

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Minho (UMinho),
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National Institute
of Materials
Physics (NIMP),
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ÉCOLE
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École Centrale de
Lyon (ECL), France

Dissemination

Project website:

<https://inl.cnrs.fr/projects/nanox4estor/>

LinkedIn Group

<https://www.linkedin.com/groups/9260371/>

ResearchGate

<https://www.researchgate.net/project/Nanoscaled-ferroelectric-pseudo-binary-oxide-thin-film-supercapacitors-for-flexible-and-ultrafast-pulsed-power-electronics>

Publications

8. T. Song, V. Lenzi, J. P. B. Silva, L. Marques, I. Fina, F. Sánchez, Disentangling stress and strain effects in ferroelectric HfO₂, *Appl. Phys. Rev.* 10, 041415 (2023).

7. A. R. Jayakrishnan, B. A. Anju, S. K. P. Nair, S. Dutta, J. P.B. Silva, Recent development of lead-free relaxor ferroelectric and antiferroelectric thin films as energy storage dielectric capacitors, *Journal of the European Ceramic Society* (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeurceramsoc.2024.02.016>

6. R. M.P. Pereira, M. C. Istrate, F. G. Figueiras, V. Lenzi, B. M. Silva, M. Benamara, K. N. Romanyuk, C. Ghica, B. G. Almeida, L. Marques, M. Pereira, J. P.B. Silva, Phase transitions in ferroelectric ZrO₂ thin films, *Materials Science in Semiconductor Processing* 172, 108102 (2023).

Conference presentations and proceedings

12. A. Silva, V. Lenzi, I. Fina, F. Sánchez, J. P. B. Silva, L. Marques, Influence of the parasitic m-phase and La doping on the polarization switching dynamics of epitaxial HfO₂ thin film. E-MRS 2023 Fall Meeting, Warsaw, Poland 18-21 september 2023 (Oral presentation).

11. M. C. Istrate, R. F. Negrea, C. Ghica, J. P. B. Silva, “Study of the pure ZrO₂ phases deposited on a Nb:SrTiO₃ substrate with different orientations using TEM/HRTEM techniques”. E-MRS 2023 Fall Meeting, Warsaw, Poland 18-21 september 2023 (Oral presentation).

10. J. P. B. Silva, “Ferroelectric ZrO₂ thin films”. Seminar to the Huawei I&D Department in Leuven and Beijing. 20 December 2023. Organized by Dr. Ming Jin, R&D Senior Engineer at Huawei Technologies Belgium Research Center (virtual).

9. M. C. Istrate, C. Ghica, J. P. B. Silva, “New deposition method for achieving ferroelectric orthorhombic ZrO₂”, Conference of the Romanian Electron Microscopy Society - C.R.E.M.S., Cluj-Napoca, 18-21 October 2023. (Poster presentation).

Technical seminar to Huawei Technologies

NanOx4EStor research work received attraction from Huawei Technologies. Dr. José Silva and Prof. Luís Marques were invited to give a technical seminar to the Huawei I&D Department in Leuven and Beijing.

NanOx4EStor research highlighted as a featured article in *Applied Physics Reviews*

Disentangling stress and strain effects in ferroelectric HfO₂

Ferroelectric HfO₂ films are usually polycrystalline and contain a mixture of polar and nonpolar phases. This challenges the understanding and control of polar phase stabilization and ferroelectric properties. Stress generated during deposition or annealing of thin films is a main factor determining the formed crystal phases and influences the lattice strain of the polar orthorhombic phase. It is difficult to discriminate between stress and strain effects on polycrystalline ferroelectric HfO₂ films, and the direct impact of orthorhombic lattice strain on ferroelectric polarization has yet to be determined experimentally. Here, UMinho team analyzes stress and strain effects on the ferroelectric properties of doped HfO₂ epitaxial films.

Fluorite-structured materials for Nanosupercapacitor Applications

To develop innovative and cost-effective supercapacitors, in this first trial, performances of Hf_{1-x}Zr_xO₂ monolayers, showing Linear Dielectric (LD), Ferroelectric (FE), and Antiferroelectric (AFE) behavior, are evaluated. A wake-up effect is noted for AFE ZrO₂, which is rarely mentioned in the literature, and compared with the pinched hysteresis disappearance in Zr-doped HfO₂ (HZO). A phenomenon which, on the contrary, has been very often observed. Energy Storage Density (ESD) and efficiency (η) comparisons reveal higher ESD for FE, but ridiculously low η. Conversely, LD samples have nearly 100% efficiency but extremely low ESD. AFE ZrO₂ monolayer balances FE and LD, with reduced losses and high ESD. Very few articles demonstrate higher ESD and η values compared to ours, indicating promising prospects for future optimization.

Ecole Centrale de Lyon (ECL) research team, in the framework of M-ERA.NET project Nanox4EStor, visited the UMinho team on 19 December 2023, at the Campus of Gualtar, in Braga. The purpose of this visit was to discuss current and future work and enhance interactions between the research teams. Dr. Alexandre Silva and Dr. Jordan Bouaziz presented the on-going work in the meeting.

Professor Judith Driscoll from the University of Cambridge and also member of the Advisory Board of the M-ERA.NET project Nanox4EStor, visited the UMinho team from 28th October up to 1st November 2023, at the Campus of Gualtar, in Braga. The purpose of this visit was to discuss current and future research work to be developed in the framework of the project.

